

Effect of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and Leadership on Employee Performance: Empirical Evidence from Smes in Indonesia Tourism-Gondang Educational Tourism Outbound (WEGO)

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Abstract:- Companies or organizations will not be separated from Human Resources. With the support of good resources and added leadership, the company can achieve goals and optimal performance. This study aims to determine and analyze the Influence of Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) and Leadership on Employee Performance in Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO). This research uses a quantitative study and the number of respondents in this study is 35 respondents. This study used documentation and questionnaire data collection techniques. The data obtained was then processed using SPSS 16 with the data analysis technique Multiple Linear Analysis, T Test and F Test and had passed various Descriptive Analysis Tests, Validity Tests, Reliability Tests and Classical Assumption Tests. Based on the results of research that has been conducted regarding the Influence of Organizational and Leadership on Employee Performance in Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO) the results show that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) has no significant effect on Employee Performance of Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO), and Leadership (X2) has a significant influence on Employee Performance on the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO)

Keywords:- Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB), Leadership, Employee Performance.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the development and many human needs, many new businesses have emerged which make competition between organizations more complex and competitive. Organizations or companies that want to continue to survive and do more to improve and make a winning company must provide superior value and quality, both service company organizations and goods/product company organizations.

To produce something of superior value, goods or service company organizations cannot be separated from good human resource factors. With the support of companies that have the best resources, they will directly get high performance for the company.

Good human resource factors are not fixed on certain skills, knowledge or competencies. But from other aspects that can increase employee awareness. or members of the organization in fulfilling its obligations. In addition, there needs to be a continuous relationship between employees or members of the organization with each other to carry out each task smoothly and for the sake of the continuity of the company's activities.

A state of mutual understanding and mutual understanding. This can also be an effective way to coordinate activities in the work environment. Even doing voluntary work outside of the job description and role demands will contribute to the effective functioning of an organization. This behavior is commonly called Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB).

The nature of OCB has a good impact on the company. As Abrar (2019) said, "A successful organization or company does not only need employees who can do more than the assigned tasks, but achieve performance that exceeds expectations. According to Riggio (2009) in Astuti et al. (2019:32) Organizations can achieve their goals if employees can carry out tasks according to their job descriptions and are willing to perform tasks other than their job descriptions.

Not only that, leadership also plays a very important role in employee performance and directly influences the company to achieve its goals. The success and achievement of the goals of a company is determined by leadership through the skills of a leader. Companies can achieve optimal performance and goals through proper leadership.

According to Sadili (2006) in Wibowo (2010: 67) To achieve the right goals a leader is needed who is able to move and convince others to work together under his leadership. Peter and Austin (1986) in Gusti (2018: 2495) say "The importance of leaders with superior qualities in improving quality". Gusti (2018: 2495) also adds "Leadership is a process whereby a person can become a leader through ongoing activities and influence the people who lead them to achieve their organizational or business goals".

Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism or what is often called WEGO is one of the well-known tourist objects in Lamongan. WEGO is located in Juwet Hamlet, Deketagung Village, Sugio District, Lamongan Regency. WEGO is an educational tourism place (edu tourism) which not only emphasizes tourist attractions but also basic education about nature. At first, WEGO was known by the iconic features of the unused BOEING 737 aircraft. But then this used BOEING 737 was updated to become WEGO Air, a real plane which is a learning vehicle called this place surrounded by lush teak debt. The air in this place is also quite beautiful because the WEGO location is in the middle of a forest. This tourist panorama is very distinctive because it is directly adjacent to the Gondang Reservoir.

Based on the description above, the researcher is interested in further researching regarding OCB and Leadership in the Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO) in Lamongan. OCB and leadership are very interesting to study because there are various aspects or elements of the relationship between employees and the impact on the company to be oriented towards increasing productivity by improving facilities and services for Lamongan Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO) tourism objects.

➤ *If the explanation is based on this background, problems are obtained, including:*

- Is OCB effect on employee performance at Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO) Lamongan?
- Does Leadership affect employee performance at Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO) Lamongan?
- If simultaneously, *organizational citizenship behavior* and leadership have an influence on employee performance on the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO) Lamongan?

➤ *The purpose of this research is to answer all the questions that have been previously formulated by examining the variables used in the research, namely:*

- Analyzing *organizational citizenship behavior* has an influence on employee performance on Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO) Lamongan
- Analyzing whether leadership affects employee performance at Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO) Lamongan
- *organizational citizenship behavior and leadership* simultaneously whether it affects the performance of Lamongan Gondang Outbound Education Tourism (WEGO) employees

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

➤ *Organizational Citizenship Behavior*

OCB is an act of more roles for each employee that is beneficial to the organization. According to Titisari (2014: 5) Organizational Citizenship Behavior, namely the act of individual contribution outside the scope of the task or outside the task requirements while working.

Organ (1997) in Titisari (2014: 6) also proposes regarding the notion of Organizational Citizenship Behavior is a person's independent actions either directly or implicitly related to rewards, and can lead to increased performance.

If formulated, Organizational Citizenship Behavior is an extra individual role action that benefits co-workers or benefits co-workers and cannot be grown solely because of the appreciation factor.

➤ *Leadership*

Gibson et al (1999) in Lina (2014: 82) state leadership as an effort to use non-coercive types of influence to motivate people to achieve certain goals.

While Wibowo (2010: 4) argues that leadership is basically the study of people with physical, mental, and positional characteristics that are considered superior to other people in a group so that they can influence other people in a group to achieve a goal. objective.

Meanwhile, according to Arianty et al. (2015:81) The ability to have an impact so that other people can be ordered and influenced to work in line with their wishes.

If formulated, leadership is the ability to get things done by commanding and influencing others to achieve goals.

➤ *Employee Performance*

According to Siagian (2006) in Indrasari (2017: 51) said performance is the result or result of many things, such as: skills, fatigue, weaknesses, and potential, useful in determining goals, paths, and individual career development plans, especially organizations or companies.

Hasibuan (2001) in Abrar (2019: 108) states that performance is an individual who can achieve job acquisition and is able to complete the work given based on ability, flying hours and seriousness and achievement.

If employee performance is formulated, namely the level of achievement of an activity from the responsibilities assigned to employees which in the process of completion are based on employee skills, experience and sincerity as well as completion time.

➤ *Relationship between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Employee Performance*

An employee in his performance can be influenced significantly and positively by Organizational citizenship behavior. The positive impact of an organization or company on the better the performance, the higher the Organizational Citizenship Behavior of its employees. (Abrar, 2019).

Barlian & Jaelani (2020) also stated that Organizational Citizenship Behavior has a role in assessing the effectiveness of employee performance appraisal. Organizational Citizenship Behavior as an alternative performance appraisal in an informal manner in order to achieve company goals. Because the more competent human resources the goals of the organization will be achieved productively, efficiently and effectively.

➤ *Relationship of Leadership to Employee Performance*

Siagian (1999) argues that the success of an organization either in division or as a whole organization is highly dependent on the quality of leadership. Leadership in an organization in achieving organizational goals has a decisive function.

Priansa in Barlian & Jaelani (2020) argues that in an organization or company the leadership of a leader really influences employees to realize organizational goals with enthusiasm so that performance can increase.

➤ *Conceptual Framework*

Based on the description that has been submitted, the conceptual model of this research is obtained in the figure below:

Fig 1 Conceptual Framework

➤ *Hypothesis Development*

Margono (2004) in Radjab (2017: 54) The hypothesis is an initial response to theoretical research presumptions considered to be the highest or most correct level of probability. In this study, researchers hypothesize:

- It is suspected that employee performance is significantly influenced by *organizational citizenship behavior* on the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO)
- It is suspected that employee performance is significantly influenced by leadership in the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO)
- It is suspected that employee performance is simultaneously and significantly influenced by *organizational citizenship behavior* and leadership in the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO)

➤ *Research Methods*

This study uses a quantitative study method. according to Sugiyono (2012) in Hotiana (2018: 30) states that if the presentation of data is numerical and statistical, then it can be said to be a quantitative method.

There are three variables in this study with two independent variables and one dependent variable. Two independent variables namely for X1 is *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (X1) and for X2 is Leadership. While the dependent variable, namely Y, is employee performance.

➤ *As for indicators of organizational citizenship behavior according to Organ et all in Titisari (2014: 07) is*

- The Nature of Altruism
- The trait of Conscientiousness
- Sportsmanship trait
- Courtesy nature
- The nature of Civic Virtu

➤ *While indicators of leadership variables according to Wahjosumidjo (1991:94) are*

- Can be fair
- Can give suggestions
- Can support goals
- As a Catalyst
- Can Create a sense of security
- Can act as a representative of the organization
- Become a Source of inspiration
- Be respectful

➤ *Meanwhile, according to Indrasari (2017: 55) for employee performance variables are as follows:*

- Work quality
- Working quantity
- Knowledge
- Reliability
- Presence
- Cooperation

Primary data used in this study was from filling out questionnaires by employees of the Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism (WEGO). While this research also collects data or sources both from companies, previous

research and other reliable references, it can be said to be secondary research data.

All employees at the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO), namely as many as 35 employees, were made into research populists or populations. Sugiono (2015) in Hotiana (2018: 30) explains the population is the conclusions drawn and investigated which have a general scope based on things or cases along with definite levels and characteristics and what determines is the research itself.

Researchers used the entire population as a sample because there were only 35 people. Arikunto (2005: 120) states that if the population is <100, then it is better to take all of them so that the research is a census research. Furthermore, if the population is > 100, 10% - 15% or 20% - 30% is taken between these percentages.

Documentation and questionnaires are used to find and collect data. Five score tests from the answers and the Likert scale are used in this series of data processing. From the results of filling in then processed through the SPSS 16 program. While the documentation needed in this study is a company profile, company vision and mission, data on the number of employees, organizational structure.

This research uses descriptive analysis. According to Sugiyono (2017) in Hadi (2018: 107) Descriptive analysis is a calculation used to describe the data collected in such a way and to analyze the data without intending to draw general conclusions or generalizations.

Multiple linear analysis is used in this research analysis tool. The magnitude of the influence between variables, namely *organizational citizenship behavior* as X1 and leadership as X2 with employee performance as variable Y can be identified using multiple linear analysis.

Determinant coefficient test is also used in this study. According to Ghozali (2013: 97) The coefficient of determination (R²) mainly calculates the distance where the model has the ability to explain the many dependent variables. Between 0 and 1 is the result of the coefficient of determination. A small result in the coefficient of determination means the ability of the independent variable to represent the limitations of the various forms of the dependent variable. The results are close to 1, then the ability of the independent variable in the prediction of the dependent variable can provide all the necessary information.

Researchers hypothesize about temporary answers so this research requires a hypothesis test. Sugiyono (2017: 64) states that "A hypothesis is a formulation of a research problem in a temporary answer, where the form of a question sentence states a formulation of a research problem. The answers given are said to be temporary because they are only based on theory and data collection to obtain facts according to experience.

The T test and F test are research tools used to find an answer to the researcher's hypothesis. The T test according to Ghozali (2018: 88) is used as a test for each independent variable affecting the dependent variable. Maintaining a significance level of 0.05 to get the t table number then compare the t table number with the calculated t value.

While simultaneous testing, namely the F test according to Sunyoto (2011) in Hotiana (2018: 33) the F test is carried out together with the test comparing F count and F table to find out the similarities or differences between variables.

This research will pass the validity test phase. According to Arikunto (2013: 211) "Validity is the validity or expertise of an instrument that is used as a parameter. Research means are valid if their validity is high. Research tools are said to be invalid if their validity is low.

This study also passed the reliability test. According to Hadi (2018: 113) Reliability is a measurement that has high reliability parameters. While Sugiyono (2017: 130) states "The same as the object and the same as the data results from the measurement results is a test of reliability"

Because the process of regression analysis must pass the classical assumption test steps. If there are no signs of classical assumptions, expect reliability in a regression model so that it is in line with the BLUE rules (*Best Linear Unbiased Estimator*), the result is unreliable and reliable regression as an estimator (Bawono, 2006: 115). This study also uses the classical assumption test which includes multicollinearity test, heteroscedasticity test and normality test.

The multicollinearity test is used which aims to test the regression model whether there is a correlation between the independent variables. The independent variable must be a good regression model with no relationship. (Ghozali, 2013:105).

While the heteroscedasticity test according to Priyatno (2008:41) is used to examine deviations from the classical assumptions, namely For each observation in the regression model, there is an inequality of variance in the residuals. "Homoscedasticity is a good regression model or heteroscedasticity is a good model not to exist" (Ghozali, 2011: 139).

While the normality test according to Ghozali (2013: 74) aims to check whether in a regression model both the dependent variable and the independent variable are normally distributed.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Research Result

➤ Company General Description

Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism or the common people call WEGO is one of these places, located in Lamongan district or more precisely in Juwet hamlet, Deketagung village, Sugio sub-district, Lamongan district. WEGO is a family company founded by the family of Mr. Ir. H. Suhandoyo SP and construction began in early 2015. At first the Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism area was a rice field area that was drained by water from one of the reservoirs in Lamongan, namely the Gondang Reservoir.

The Gondang Outbound Educational Tour itself was officially opened on November 10, 2016 on a 23-hectare land surrounded by tropical forest and panoramic views of the reservoir that can be witnessed from the tourist spot. At that time the tourist sites were still sober and not what they are now, slowly WEGO finally started to go viral and was recognized by the people of Lamongan and its surroundings by relying on the BOEING 747 aircraft frame which was transformed like an airplane that still functions as an icon of WEGO.

Over time, this place has additional rides that have become mainstays such as waterparks, duck lakes and bridges of love. Not only that, at this time there are also other supporting facilities such as flying fox, animal area, trail arena, several pavilions, old houses containing a complete gamelan set, camping grounds, lodging and outbound & playground areas.

➤ Vision and Mission of Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism

- **Vision:**
The Realization Of Educational Tourism That Apply Natural Science And History For Tourists.

- **Mission:**
 - ✓ Educational Tourism that utilizes outbound facilities with the aim of fostering self-confidence, courage and agility.
 - ✓ Introducing the diversity of flora and fauna for tourists.
 - ✓ Historical education with various media.
 - ✓ Tours that provide pleasure and inspiration for tourists who have visited.

➤ Organizational Structure

Wego's organizational structure starts with the owner in charge of the two directors, then there is the main manager who oversees this department of the company and under him there are several divisions in charge of every vehicle in WEGO.

Fig 2 Organizational Structure

➤ Results Description Respondents

Based on this study, the characteristics include the name of the employee respondent and gender in the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour. The number of questionnaires distributed via the Google form is 37 questionnaires. Based on the recapitulation of the questionnaire, the results of the analysis of the frequency distribution of the respondents were obtained as follows:

Table 1 Respondents Description Results

Gender	Number of respondents	Percentage
Man	31	88.6%
Woman	4	11.4%
Amount	35	100%

From the table above it can be seen that the respondents who were male were 31 respondents and the respondents who were female were 4 respondents.

➤ Descriptive Analysis

In this study the method of analysis uses descriptive statistical analysis:

- **Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) Variable Frequency Data Analysis**

Based on the respondents' answers, the highest frequency was item X1.3 regarding "Employees will help orient new employees even if they are not asked." with a value of 3.63. This shows that the respondents or employees of the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour have the nature of participating in helping the organization reduce costs and time for orientation or training purposes. The lowest score is 3.09, namely item X1.5 "Employees will not spend time talking outside of work". Which means the need to reduce variance in performance and maintain time efficiency so that the level of performance consistency can be high.

• *Leadership Variable Frequency Data Analysis*

Based on the respondents' answers, the statement with the highest frequency is item X2.8 regarding "Managers provide all employees with complete information regarding the correct implementation of work orders." with a value of 3.94. This shows that leaders also provide understanding and understanding of their employees, so that the performance of employees can be maximized. The lowest score is also 3.43, namely item X2.10 "Managers make rules that allow them to manage the safety and comfort of their employees". Which means employees need to increase compliance with regulations, which are regulations themselves to achieve effective goals.

• *Analysis of Employee Performance Frequency Data Variables*

Based on the answers from the respondents that the statement with the most frequency is item Y.4 about "Employees must understand matters regarding the tasks assigned by the organization "with a value of 3.80. This shows that employees understand the *job* description or problems regarding the tasks assigned. In addition, there is the lowest score with a value of 3.57, namely item Y.3 "The total work of employees must comply with the provisions of the organization ". This shows that the need to improve performance in carrying out the tasks assigned.

➤ *Validity Test*

Table 2 Validity Test

Variable	Items	Count	Rtable	Information
X1	X1.1	0.556	0.338	Valid
	X1.2	0.91	0.338	Valid
	X1.3	0.854	0.338	Valid
	X1.4	0.883	0.338	Valid
	X1.5	0.705	0.338	Valid
	X1.6	0.848	0.338	Valid
	X1.7	0.867	0.338	Valid
	X1.8	0.86	0.338	Valid
	X1.9	0.866	0.338	Valid
	X1.10	0.912	0.338	Valid
	X1.11	0.877	0.338	Valid
	X1.12	0.903	0.338	Valid
X2	X2.1	0.686	0.338	Valid
	X2.2	0.783	0.338	Valid
	X2.3	0.88	0.338	Valid
	X2.4	0.868	0.338	Valid
	X2.5	0.827	0.338	Valid
	X2.6	0.889	0.338	Valid
	X2.7	0.78	0.338	Valid
	X2.8	0.869	0.338	Valid
	X2.9	0.841	0.338	Valid
	X2.10	0.857	0.338	Valid
	X2.11	0.888	0.338	Valid
	X2.12	0.889	0.338	Valid
	X2.13	0.73	0.338	Valid
	X2.14	0.814	0.338	Valid
	X2.15	0.699	0.338	Valid
	X2.16	0.825	0.338	Valid
Y	Y. 1	0.892	0.338	Valid

	Y.2	0.906	0.338	Valid
	Y.3	0.854	0.338	Valid
	Y.4	0.905	0.338	Valid
	Y.5	0.869	0.338	Valid
	Y.6	0.929	0.338	Valid
	Y.7	0.929	0.338	Valid
	Y. 8	0.8	0.338	Valid
	Y.9	0.883	0.338	Valid

Based on the table, it can be seen that all statements X1 to Y9 have $r_{count} > r_{table}$, which means that all data is said to be valid.

➤ *Reliability Test*

Table 3 Reliability Test

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha value	Coefficient	Information
Organization Citizenship Behavior (X1)	0.961	0.6	Reliable
Leadership (X2)	0.967	0.6	Reliable
Employee Performance (Y)	0.965	0.6	Reliable

The reliability test in this study was obtained from the results of distributing questionnaires to 35 respondents to Gondang Outbound Educational Tourism employees who had been processed and obtained in the table. The reliability test results obtained from analyzing the Cronbach Alpha value were then compared with the reliability coefficient of 0.6.

Based on the table it can be seen that the value of Cronbach Alpha > coefficient means that the items in the instrument variable are reliable.

➤ *Classic Assumption Test*

• *Multicollinearity Test*

Table 4 Multicollinearity Test

Variable	VIF	Tolerance
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1)	2.1229	0.472
Leadership (X2)	2,119	0.472

If based on table 3, VIF Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) 2, 1229 < 10.00 and a tolerance value of 0.472 > 0.10, which means that there is no multicollinearity. While the VIF value of the Leadership variable (X2) is 2.119 < 10.00 and the tolerance value is 0.472 > 0.10 which means that there is also no multicollinearity. So the conclusion of the two independent variable tests of Work Motivation (X1) and Leadership (X2) is free from multicollinearity.

• *Heteroscedasticity Test*

Figure 3 Heteroscedasticity Test

Based on the picture, it can be interpreted that there is no heteroscedasticity because the picture does not show a certain pattern and the data or dots are scattered below and above the number 0

• *Normality Test*

Table 5 Normality Test

		Unstandardized Residuals
N		35
Normal Parameters ^a	Means	0.0000000
	std. Deviation	3.71099234
Most Extreme Differences	absolute	0.145
	Positive	0.105
	Negative	-0.145
Kolmogorov-Smirnov Z		
asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)		

From table 4, the normality test obtained a significance value of 0.452 > 0.005, meaning that the data has a normal distribution .

➤ *Multiple Linear Analysis*

Table 6 Multiple Linear Analysis

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	Q	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Betas		
1 (Constant)	1.025	2,574		0.398	0.693
Total_X1	0.001	0.074	0.002	0.016	0.987
Total_X2	0.541	0.060	0.918	9,076	0.000

• Multiple linear test results with the following equation:

$$Y = 1.025 + 0.01(X1) + 0.541(X2) + e$$

➤ *Based on the Results of these Equations, it can be Interpreted as Follows:*

- Constant (a) has a value of 1.025 which can be interpreted if the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) and Leadership (X2)* variables are equal to zero, then Employee Performance is 1.025.
- The coefficient of *Organizational Citizenship Behavior (b1)* is 0.01 which indicates that *organizational citizenship behavior* has a positive effect on employee performance. This means that if there is an increase in one unit of the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable* it states that it affects employee performance by 0.01.
- leadership coefficient value (b2) is 0.541 which indicates that if the leadership variable has a positive influence on employee performance, this means that if there is an increase in one unit the leadership variable states that it has an effect on employee performance of 0.541.

➤ *Determinant Coefficient Test*

Following are the results of testing the determinant coefficient R2 using the SPSS 16 application:

Table 7 Coefficient Test

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.919 ^a	0.845	0.836	3,825

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.836, which means that Employee Performance can be explained by Organizational Citizenship Behavior and leadership of 83.6%. It can be interpreted that the value of interaction between variables in this study can affect the dependent variable by 83.6% . The rest of the variables that influence and this research does not examine these variables.

➤ *Hypothesis Testing*

• *T Test*

Table 8 T test

Indicator	T Count	T Table	Sig	Information
Organizational Characteristics Behavior (X1)	0.016	1,692	0.987	Hypothesis Rejected
Leadership (X2)	9,076	1,692	0.000	Hypothesis Accepted

Based on the table above it can be seen that:

- ✓ *Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1)*
Based on the calculation results show that for a significance value of 0.05 if the t table is 1.692. Based on table 8 it can be concluded that the results of the T test on the *Organizational Citizenship Behavior variable (X1)* on the Employee Performance variable (Y) yielded t count 0.016. So it means that the value of t count = 0.016. So that the value of t count is 0.016 <t table is 1.692. So it is stated

that *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* (X1) does not have a significant effect on Employee Performance (Y)

✓ Leadership (X2)

Based on table 8, it shows that the significance is 0.05 if the t table is 1.692. Based on table 8 it can be concluded that the results of the T test on the Leadership variable (X2) on the Employee Performance variable (Y) produce a t count of 9.076. So that the calculated t value = 0.016. So it can be concluded that the t count value is $9.076 > t$ table 1.692. So it can be concluded that leadership (X2) partially has a positive and significant effect on employee performance (Y).

• F Test

Table 9 F test

Model	F	Sig.
1. Regression	87,494	0.000a -

In this test using a significance level <0.05 , there are implications for variable X together with variable Y. It can be seen in table 8 that the significance value is $0.000 < 0.05$ and/or the calculated f value is $87.494 > 3.28$ f table. So that it can be interpreted that Organizational Citizenship Behavior (X1) and Leadership (X2) simultaneously have an influence on employee performance (Y).

IV. DISCUSSION OF RESEARCH RESULTS

Based on the test of variable X1 or *organizational citizenship behavior* and variable X2 or leadership simultaneously on employee performance, a significant value of $87.494 > 3.28$ is obtained, which means that employee performance is significantly influenced by *organizational citizenship behavior* and leadership simultaneously or simultaneously.

While the results of the analysis and tabulation of some of the results of variable X1, namely *organizational citizenship behavior* and variable X2, namely leadership on variable Y, namely employee performance on the Gondang Outbound Educational Tour, the results of the analysis obtained a significant number of 0.016 for variable X1, namely *organizational citizenship behavior*. So it can be concluded that *organizational citizenship behavior* partially does not have a significant effect on employee performance. These results indicate that *Organizational Citizenship Behavior* does not change the employee's performance or remains. From this assessment it is also in line with what was examined by Kusuma & Endratno (2021), namely employee performance in this study has no significance from the influence of *organizational citizenship behavior*.

On the other hand, the results of the analysis obtained a significant figure for the effect of leadership or X2 on employee performance or Y of 9.076. So it can be concluded that employee performance is significantly influenced by leadership partially.

This is because leadership influences employees to realize what the organization is aiming for. The results of this study are also in line with Arianty (2015), namely leadership exists and has a significant correlation with employee performance.

V. CONCLUSION

➤ Based on the research that has been carried out through various empirical stages regarding the influence of the topic title above, the following is the conclusion:

- Employee performance is simultaneously significantly and positively affected by *organizational citizenship behavior* and leadership simultaneously on the Lamongan Gondang Outbound Educational Tour (WEGO).
- However, partially, employee performance is not significantly and positively affected by *organizational citizenship behavior* on the Gondang Outbound Lamongan Educational Tour.
- On the other hand, employee performance is significantly and positively affected by leadership at the Lamongan Gondang Outbound Educational Tour.

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